

A new 3D finite element model for the mechanical analysis of random fiber composite

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Keywords: *random fiber composite, Young's modulus, 3D FE model, fiber aspect ratio, fiber fraction*

1 Introduction

In recent years, there is a growing need for random fiber composites (RaFCs) with high-aspect-ratio fibers as it possesses both higher performance and mass processibility. To expand their uses, it requires a reliable overall material properties estimated from a homogenization process that allows for an efficient analysis of large scale structures, and, in addition, a well predicted micro-level properties for the predefined macro-scale loadings.

The extension to the mean field methods based on the original work by Mori and Tanaka [1] has enjoyed much interest, particularly following the clarifications provided by Benveniste [2]. Such family of methods are employed to estimate material properties based on Eshelby's field solution [3] for single ellipsoidal inclusion in an infinite matrix. Then the overall elastic properties of composites are obtained using the orientation distribution function to average the stiffness tensor [4, 5]. Another more mechanistic set of methods, namely the laminate approximation approach (LAA) [6], have been employed to create an analogous model for RaFCs. The classical laminated plane theory is performed to compute the composite effective stiffness matrices [7, 8], by idealizing the material as a set of parallel layers. Fibers in each layer have the same length and orientation. These method have provided a rather inexpensive engineering type analysis, especially, when the fiber volume fractions of RaFCs are not very large. Furthermore, Ionita and Weitsman [9]

proposed the 'laminated random strand' model, which used a 'moving window approach' to analyze the high volume fraction carbon fiber/urethane composites.

However, the aforementioned theoretical methods and semi-empirical theories have paid few attention to the micro-mechanical stress-strain state of RaFCs, thus finite element analysis (FEA) is widely employed to model the RaFCs. Based on Hill's concept of representative volume element (RVE) [10], the direct 3D FEA is also widely employed to model the response of RaFCs [11-13]. But such RVEs have two drawbacks. First, it is difficult to generate a RVE when the fiber aspect ratio (AR) is large. Second, distorted finite element (FE) meshes may extensively appear at the local fiber contact points.

In this paper, a new automatic searching & coupling (ASC) approach is proposed to generate the 3D model with large fiber AR and volume fractions. Bypassing the limitations imposed by conventional approaches [14], the present model can be achieved at a low computational cost. The stabilization of the effective Young's modulus is used to determine the RVE size, while the coarseness parameter of the model [15] is also discussed. The mechanical properties of RaFCs are calculated using FEA, and the predicted results accord well with experimental results [16], which support the present finite element (FE) model. Finally, the FE model is employed to explore the influences of fiber length on the

effective in-plane Young's modulus and shear modulus of RaFCs.

2 Modeling the 3D RVE

2.1 Geometric Model Generation

The 3D fiber architecture is generated by a modified random sequential adsorption (RSA) algorithm in ANSYS Parametric Design Language, wherein the fibers are modeled as straight lines. To ensure the position and orientation of each fiber in 3D space, as shown in Fig. 1, three random numbers within upper and lower bounds of RVE are generated for the x, y and z coordinates of the center point of the fiber, $C(x)$, and two other random numbers are used for the Euler angles θ and ϕ of the fiber. Besides, the line is described by the uniform length L . As the lines which do not take up any space are used to represent the fibers, fiber intersections can be ignored in our FE model. Consequently, the geometric model with a large fiber AR and volume fraction can be established for RaFCs.

2.2 Finite Element Modeling

The analysis for geometric model at the mesoscopic level is implemented in the commercial FE package ANSYS13.0. Herein, the 3D beam element (Beam188) with circular cross-section is adopted to represent fibers; the matrix, modeled as Solid185, is represented by a regular array of solid elements. In the present FE model, the deformations of fibers and the matrix are matched by the ASC technology, which is based on the assumption of perfect interfacial bonding.

Fig. 2 shows a sketch for the ASC technology. The node N_s of the solid element represented by the right green hexahedron is the center of the left hollow hexahedron which has the same size as the former. In fact N_s becomes the adjacent solid of any fiber nodes in the hollow hexahedron, one of which is represented by N_f as shown in Fig. 2. The translational freedom degrees of N_f are coupled with those of N_s . Clearly the precision of the present approach is sufficient when the mesh is fine enough.

In addition, the axial rotational freedom degree of each beam element is fixed by defining a constraint equation to relate the three rotational freedom degrees of a random node of the beam. The ASC technology avoids the complex meshing algorithm, and is therefore timesaving during the generation of FE model.

By applying the 3D periodic boundary conditions, the present FE model can be used to predict the anisotropic properties of RaFCs. The material properties used for all FE analyses in the current work are listed in Table 1, which are the same as those in series A of Ref. [16] to facilitate the comparison in section 3.3.

2.3 Comparison with conventional mesh

Fig. 3 shows the model using the ASC technology and the model using a more conventional free meshing approach. In the two types of FE model, the fiber distributions are identical and the RVE sizes are both $600\mu\text{m}\times 600\mu\text{m}\times 120\mu\text{m}$. Other identical properties for fibers and matrix are listed in Table 1. In the irregular meshed model, the fiber nodes are merged with the coincident matrix nodes for assuming perfect interfacial bonding. In the ASC model, the element size is $15\mu\text{m}\times 15\mu\text{m}\times 6\mu\text{m}$.

A comparison of Von Mises stress between the aforementioned two types of model for the tensile loading in plane along x direction is made in Fig. 4. It shows that the stress fields and the deformation shapes are almost identical. After that, the two types of models are used to evaluate the effective elastic constants for RaFCs. As shown in Table 2, the errors of effective elastic constants are all smaller than 0.2%, among which E_{22} has the biggest error of 0.12% in the effective moduli and ν_{32} has the biggest error of 0.19% in the effective Poisson's ratios.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 RVE size criterion

Although the periodicity boundary condition ensures the deterministic Hill condition, the critical RVE

size larger than 1 time of the fiber length L has been used in many works. Otherwise, fibers might bridge the cell (cross two boundaries) and be directly loaded by the boundary conditions. Thus the convergence point of the effective modulus will be used as the critical RVE size in the current work.

Fig. 5 shows the average value and standard deviations of in-plane Young's modulus E_{11} , shear modulus G_{12} , and out-plane Young's modulus E_{33} , respectively, with the change of RVE dimension a in plane (results are normalized by the fiber length L). It is necessary to point out that the relative error of E_{22} has also been calculated. The error between E_{11} and E_{22} is generally less than 5%, and hence the curves of E_{22} have not been presented. It shows that the average value of E_{11} and G_{12} is not stable until $a/L=1.33$, in contrast that the average value of E_{33} is always stable with the increment of RVE size. In addition, the standard deviations of each effective modulus decrease as the RVE size increases.

The error between the point $a/L=1.33$ and the next available data point $a/L=1.67$ is less than 1% for the average value of E_{11} and E_{33} , while less than 1.5% error for G_{12} . Thus convergence point of each of the effective modulus occurs when $a/L=1.33$ ($a=4\text{mm}$), satisfying the size criterion.

3.2 Coarseness parameter

The level of fiber homogeneity also impacts the rate of convergence of the effective elastic properties. The approach of describing the RVEs and studying the local volume fraction V_f mentioned in Ref. [17] has been applied here. A coarseness parameter Λ has been calculated to provide a quantitative measure of non-uniformity in fiber range, i.e.

$$\Lambda = \frac{1}{\bar{V}_f} \sqrt{\langle V_f^2 \rangle - \bar{V}_f^2} \quad (1)$$

where \bar{V}_f is the average global volume fraction of the RVE and $\langle V_f^2 \rangle$ is the ensemble average of the local square volume fraction. For homogeneity materials, Eq. (1) yields a value of zero.

As presented in Fig. 6, the average values and standard deviations of coarseness parameter Λ of the previous RVEs decrease with increasing RVE size for the three different fiber volume fractions. The average Λ is also below 10% when the critical RVE size ($a=4\text{mm}$) is achieved. It is obvious that the trend of Λ is the same as the cases in Ref. [17, 18].

3.3 Comparison with the experimental results

The in-plane Young's modulus E_{11} is calculated by the present FE model whose parameters set are taken from the chopped glass-fiber reinforced polypropylene composite (*series A*) [16]. The FEA results and experimental data, corresponding to RaFCs with various fiber weight fractions and constant 3mm fiber length, are listed in Table 3. As the fiber weight fractions are used in Ref. [16], we transform the volume fractions, which are used in the FE models, into the weight fractions.

It shows that the FEA results and the experimental data have the biggest relative error of 3.86% when the weight fraction is 20% (7.95%vf), while those have the smallest error of 0.97% when the weight fraction is 25% (10.33%vf). Therefore, the results obtained by FE models accord well with the experimental results. In addition, the effective Young's moduli evaluated by FE models are all smaller than the experimental results except when the weight fraction is 10% (3.70%vf).

3.4 Effective Young's modulus

Fig. 7 shows the influences of fiber AR on the effective Young's modulus, involving three different fiber volume fractions. It is obvious that the variation of E_{11} with AR is nonlinear for the three different fiber volume fractions: E_{11} of the RaFCs increases significantly with AR when the latter is smaller than 100; for a larger AR, the enhanced influences can be neglected. Besides, the distances between the curve of 5%vf and the curve of 10%vf is the nearly same as the distances between the curve of 10%vf and the curve of 15%vf. It implies that the increasing of E_{11} with the fiber volume fraction is

linear, which agrees well with the fitting results in Ref. [16].

3.5 Effective shear modulus

The effective shear modulus G_{12} is shown in Fig. 8 as a function of fiber AR, involving three different fiber volume fractions. The trend of the G_{12} curves is similar with that of the E_{11} curves presented in Fig. 7. The curves are also nonlinear while the turning point is nearly at AR of 100 as well. Since the RaFCs are transversely isotropic materials, it is obvious that the in-plane Young's modulus and shear modulus have the same trend.

4 Remarks

A modified RSA algorithm has been used for producing spatial distributions of randomly orientated, discontinuous fibers. A new ASC technology has been proposed to yield simplified meshes for FEA and to facilitate the direct application of 3D periodic boundary conditions on the model. To validate the effectiveness of the ASC technology and the FE model in the current paper, we have done the following work:

- (1) A comparison has been conducted between the ASC technology and the conventional free meshing approach in a special case. It shows that the error of effective elastic properties yielded by the two approaches is less than 0.2%.
- (2) The convergence point of the effective modulus has been employed to determine the critical size of RVEs with different fiber volume fractions. The coarseness parameter for RVEs is also discussed. It indicates that the RVE dimension of 4mm ($a/L=1.33$) is fit for the critical size of RVEs for FEA.
- (3) The FEA results have been compared with the existing experimental data [16]. It shows that the results predicted by the FE model accord well with the experimental data.

After the effectiveness has been proved, the in-plane effective Young's modulus E_{11} and shear modulus

G_{12} have been evaluated by using the FE model. It shows that the variation of E_{11} and G_{12} is nonlinear in change with the fiber AR but is linear in change with the fiber volume fraction. Besides, E_{11} and G_{12} have similar trends, which accords with the transversely isotropic behavior of RaFCs.

Compared with other available models, it is noteworthy that the ASC technology and the present FE model can provide a direct prediction for the elastic modulus of RaFCs with a large fiber AR and volume fraction.

Acknowledgments

The authors thank the support from the National Natural Science Foundation of China (11272030, 11072015).

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Table 1. Summary of parameters used in the FE models.

Fiber Young's modulus	E_f (GPa)	75
Fiber Poisson's ratio	ν_f	0.25
Fiber shear modulus	G_f (GPa)	30
Matrix Young's modulus	E_m (GPa)	1.6
Matrix Poisson's ratio	ν_m	0.35
Matrix shear modulus	G_m (GPa)	0.59
Fiber diameter	d_f (μm)	13

Table 2. The comparison of the effective elastic constants between the ASC model and the free meshing model.

	ASC	Free meshing	Error (%)
E_{11} (GPa)	1.6932	1.6937	0.03
E_{22} (GPa)	1.7208	1.7228	0.12
E_{33} (GPa)	1.6402	1.6407	0.03
G_{12} (GPa)	0.6409	0.6407	0.02
G_{13} (GPa)	0.5903	0.5900	0.06
G_{23} (GPa)	0.5903	0.5890	0.05
ν_{12}	0.3546	0.3550	0.12
ν_{21}	0.3489	0.3490	0.03
ν_{13}	0.3397	0.3395	0.04
ν_{31}	0.3506	0.3505	0.04
ν_{23}	0.3476	0.3472	0.11
ν_{32}	0.3313	0.3307	0.19

Table 3. Comparison of the FEA results with the experimental data.

WT fraction (%)	Vol fraction (%)	Composite Young's modulus E11 (GPa)		Error (%)
		Experiment	FEA	
10	3.70	2.43	2.46	1.23
20	7.95	3.63	3.49	3.86
25	10.33	4.11	4.07	0.97
30	12.89	4.84	4.69	3.10
40	18.72	6.20	6.07	2.10

Fig. 1. Modeling a fiber as a straight line in 3D space.

Fig. 2. The sketch for the ASC technology.

Fig. 3. The sketches for meshes and fibers distribution. The red lines represent the random fibers. (a) The matrix is meshed with a regular array of solid elements by the ASC technology ; (b) The matrix is meshed by a free approach.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. The comparison of Von Mises stress between the matrix meshed (a) by the ASC technology and (b) by the free approach for tensile loading along x direction.

Fig. 5. Effect of increasing RVE size on the effective stiffness.

Fig. 6. Coarseness parameter (Eq. (1)) as a function of RVE dimension a in plane normalized by fiber length L .

Fig. 7. The effective in-plane Young's modulus E_{11} as a function of fiber aspect ratio.

Fig. 8. The effective in-plane shear modulus G_{12} as a function of fiber aspect ratio.